

Sectoral Credit Allocation and Economic Growth in Nigeria: A Comparative Analysis of Oil, Manufacturing, and Agriculture

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between sector-specific credit allocation to the agricultural, manufacturing, and oil sectors and economic growth in Nigeria. The results showed that credit to the agricultural sector positively affected economic growth, indicating that targeted financing enhances production capacity, livelihoods, and per capita income, even though some effects were small or statistically insignificant, highlighting the need for additional policies to improve productivity. Conversely, credit to the manufacturing sector had a negative correlation with growth, suggesting that inefficiencies in credit use, structural issues, or misaligned lending can prevent the effective transformation of financial resources into productive output. Credit to the oil sector had a positive effect, reflecting its crucial role in government revenue, foreign exchange earnings, and investment flows. Overall, the findings imply that the growth impact of sector-specific credit depends on proper allocation, the sector's ability to absorb funds, and a supportive macroeconomic and policy environment. The agriculture and oil sectors showed the strongest positive effects, while manufacturing credit requires better management to foster growth.

Keywords: sectoral credit, economic growth, agriculture, manufacturing, oil sector

Introduction

Despite Nigeria's abundant resources, especially in the oil sector, the country has experienced unimpressive and volatile economic growth over the years. The Nigerian economy remains heavily dependent on oil, which makes up a large portion of government revenue and foreign exchange earnings. However, this dependence on oil has created vulnerability to global oil price swings, hindering economic diversification and sustainable growth (Abubakar & Akadiri, 2022). As a result, sectors like manufacturing and agriculture, which have the potential to diversify the economy and foster inclusive growth, remain underfunded, and credit to these sectors is insufficient (Fapetu & Obalade, 2018).

The existing literature on the relationship between sectoral credit allocation and economic growth in Nigeria is limited, especially when it involves a comprehensive comparison of the oil, manufacturing, and agriculture sectors. While some studies have focused on the importance of credit allocation to the oil sector in driving economic growth (Muthusamy et al., 2018), others have emphasized the need for more credit to manufacturing and agriculture to promote economic diversification (Sogules & Nkoro, 2016). However, few studies have compared the impact of credit allocation across all three sectors, and even fewer have utilized a detailed time series analysis from 2000 Q1 to 2023 Q4, leaving a notable gap in the literature.

This gap in the literature highlights the need for a focused study comparing how sectoral credit allocation in the oil, manufacturing, and agricultural sectors affects Nigeria's economic growth. Understanding how these sectors contribute differently to growth through credit is crucial for developing policies that promote a more balanced and resilient economy (Ighosewe et al., 2021). By addressing this gap, the study aims to offer valuable insights into how Nigeria can improve credit allocation to support sustainable economic growth and lessen its reliance on the volatile oil sector (Osakwe & Akunna, 2022).

Objectives of the Research

The general objective of this study is to investigate Sectoral credit allocation and Economic growth in Nigeria: A comparative analysis of Oil, manufacturing, and Agriculture. However, the specific objectives include to:

1. Investigate the effect of credit allocation to the agricultural sector on economic growth in Nigeria.
2. Examine the impact of credit allocation to the manufacturing sector on economic growth in Nigeria.
3. Ascertain the effect of credit allocation to the oil sector on economic growth in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

- H01: Credit allocation to the agricultural sector does not significantly affect economic growth in Nigeria
- H02: Credit allocation to the manufacturing sector does not significantly affect economic growth in Nigeria
- H03: Credit allocation to the oil sector does not significantly influence economic growth in Nigeria

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Concept of economic growth

Economic growth refers to the increase in the output of goods and services in an economy over time. In the Nigerian context, the concept of economic growth has been defined in several ways, reflecting different aspects of the country's development trajectory. One common definition emphasizes the growth in Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which indicates the total value of goods and services produced within a country's borders (Abubakar & Akadiri, 2022). Another perspective links economic growth to industrialization and diversification, especially away from the oil sector, to create a more balanced and resilient economy (Ighosewe et al., 2021). A third definition focuses on human development indicators such as improved living standards, education, and healthcare, which align more closely with sustainable and inclusive economic growth (Osakwe & Akunna, 2022). Each definition provides a valuable perspective on what constitutes growth, depending on the focus of analysis.

Among the various definitions of economic growth in Nigeria, this study uses per capita income as a proxy. This choice is based on the belief that per capita income better reflects individuals' living standards within an economy, as it considers population size. Unlike GDP, which measures total national output without factoring in the well-being of the population, per capita income offers a clearer indicator of economic welfare by adjusting for population growth (Akinleye et al., 2021). This is especially important for Nigeria, where rapid population growth and income disparities across regions and sectors remain significant (Muthusamy et al., 2018).

Economic growth can be assessed using various indicators, each highlighting different aspects of economic development. GDP growth is the most traditional and widely used measure, reflecting the overall expansion of an economy. However, GDP does not consider income distribution, nor does it provide insights into individuals' well-being (Ighosewe et al., 2021). Other measures include Gross National Product (GNP), which adjusts GDP by accounting for net income from abroad, and the Human Development Index (HDI), which includes education, life expectancy, and income levels. Despite these alternatives, per capita income remains one of the most recognized and dependable indicators for understanding the economic conditions of individuals in an economy (Majeed & Iftikhar, 2020).

Using per capita income as the measure for economic growth is grounded in its ability to better reflect individual prosperity. Unlike GDP, which sums up national production without considering population size, per capita income adjusts for demographic changes, providing a more accurate picture of how the average person is experiencing economic growth (Abubakar & Akadiri, 2022). Given Nigeria's large

and growing population, this measure helps to better understand how economic growth is spread across different parts of society. It also reveals disparities in wealth and living standards, which are important for assessing whether Nigeria's growth is inclusive and sustainable (Osakwe & Akunna, 2022).

Sectoral Credits and Their Implications for Nigeria's Economic Growth

Sectoral credit allocation involves distributing financial resources, such as loans or credit, across different sectors of an economy to foster growth and development within those sectors. One definition highlights the role of financial institutions in directing credit to various sectors based on their contribution to the economy and their growth potential (Abubakar & Akadiri, 2022). Another definition connects sectoral credit allocation to the priorities established by governments or central banks, aiming to promote specific sectors to reach national economic objectives like diversification or poverty alleviation (Ighosewe et al., 2021). A third definition emphasizes the importance of balanced credit distribution to ensure all sectors, especially underfunded ones like agriculture, receive sufficient financing to increase productivity and employment (Fapetu & Obalade, 2018).

For this study, the adopted definition views sectoral credit allocation as the strategic distribution of credit across different economic sectors, aimed at promoting balanced and sustainable economic growth. It involves intentionally directing financial resources to boost key sectors like agriculture, manufacturing, and oil, each of which has a unique role in Nigeria's economic landscape (Akinleye et al., 2021). This definition supports the study's goal of analysing how sectoral credit distribution influences economic growth and development by assessing the contributions of these sectors.

The segments of sectoral credit allocations in Nigeria include agricultural, manufacturing, and oil sector credits. Agricultural sector credits focus on providing financial resources to farming and agricultural activities, enabling increased food production, rural development, and employment (Osakwe & Akunna, 2022). Manufacturing sector credits are directed toward industries that process raw materials into finished goods, contributing to industrialization and diversification away from oil dependence (Muthusamy et al., 2018). Oil sector credits, on the other hand, refer to financial resources allocated to exploration, production, and distribution within the oil industry, which has historically been the main driver of Nigeria's economic growth, despite its vulnerability to global price changes (Ighosewe et al., 2021). Each sector plays a critical role in shaping the country's overall economic structure and its growth trajectory.

Theoretical Review

Financial Intermediation Theory

The Financial Intermediation Theory stems from the work of economists who aimed to understand how financial intermediaries, like banks and other lending institutions, contribute to economic growth. This theory assumes that financial intermediaries are essential in enabling the efficient allocation of resources by collecting savings from households and channeling them into productive investments across various sectors (Muthusamy et al., 2018). It also suggests that intermediaries help reduce information asymmetry between borrowers and lenders, mitigate risks, and allocate credit according to the needs of different economic sectors. Through this process, financial intermediation is believed to improve the efficiency of capital markets and foster economic growth by directing credit toward productive activities.

In this study, the Financial Intermediation Theory is relevant because it offers a framework for understanding how credit moves from financial institutions to main economic sectors. The theory indicates that credit allocation to the agricultural, manufacturing, and oil sectors can impact economic growth by enabling investment, increasing productivity, and fostering innovation (Ighosewe et al., 2021). By analysing how credit is distributed among these sectors, the study can examine how financial intermediaries aid economic development and how the effective or ineffective distribution of credit

influences per capita income and overall growth. This theoretical framework is especially useful for understanding the role of banks and development institutions in driving sectoral growth in Nigeria.

However, the Financial Intermediation Theory has certain limitations and weaknesses. One major limitation is its assumption that financial intermediaries always allocate credit efficiently, which may not always be the case in practice due to issues such as poor governance, corruption, or mismanagement of funds (Abubakar & Akadiri, 2022). Additionally, the theory assumes that all sectors have equal access to credit, but in reality, sectors like agriculture often face challenges such as high interest rates, inadequate collateral, and limited financial literacy, which hinder access to funding (Osakwe & Akunna, 2022). These constraints suggest that financial intermediaries may not always be able to effectively channel credit to sectors that need it most, thus limiting the theory's practical applicability in some contexts.

Review of Empirical Literature

Adegoriola and Ishaku (2023) investigated how credit allocation by Deposit Money Banks (DMB) to the agricultural and manufacturing sectors affects the performance of the Nigerian economy from 1986 to 2020. They used the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to assess both short-term and long-term effects, along with Granger causality tests to determine the direction of causality. The ARDL bounds test indicates long-term co-integration among the variables. The results showed that DMB credit to the manufacturing sector had a negative and insignificant impact on economic growth in both the first and second lags. Likewise, credit to the agricultural sector had a positive but insignificant influence on growth. The Granger causality test found no causal relationship between DMB credit to the manufacturing and agricultural sectors and economic growth.

Ogbonna et al. (2023) examined the effect of bank credit on sectors such as agriculture, mining, quarrying, manufacturing, and government on Nigeria's economic development (HDI) from 1986 to 2020. The study used the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method, with data collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and the World Bank Data Atlas. The results showed a long-term and short-term connection between bank credit and HDI. Nonetheless, bank credit to agriculture and government displayed a negative and insignificant relationship with HDI, whereas bank credit to the manufacturing sector had a notable impact. Bank credit to the mining and quarrying sectors had an insignificant effect on HDI.

In the study by Odido, Effiong, and Eneje (2023), the focus shifted to examining how crude oil price fluctuations impact the growth rate of the Nigerian economy. Using an ex-post facto research design with data from 1997 to 2022, the study found no significant link between crude oil price changes and the Nigerian economy's growth rate. The results indicated a possible imbalance caused by the effects of crude oil exports and refined oil imports. Recommendations included diversifying the economy into sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and tourism to lessen reliance on the oil sector.

Gbadamosi, Ayoola, and Adeosun (2022) explored the effect of four key variables—crude oil price, real exchange rate, inflation, and population—on Nigeria's economic growth. The study used annual time series data from the World Development Indicator (WDI). Johansen Cointegration test and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) were performed to identify the cointegrating relationship among the variables. The results clearly indicated that crude oil price, real exchange rate, inflation, and population significantly impacted the response variable (GDP) in both the short and long run. Fluctuations in crude oil prices negatively affected Nigeria's economic growth, real exchange rate, and contributed to inflationary increases in the country over the long term.

Abubakar and Akadiri (2022) examined the effects of oil rents and revenues on economic growth in Nigeria. They used novel dynamic ARDL simulation and Kernel Regularized Least Squares (KRLS) with annual time series data from 1973 to 2020. They found that oil rents are insignificant and have decreasing marginal effects on economic growth in Nigeria, while oil revenue has a significant and sustainable impact on economic growth.

Mbelu and Ifionu (2022) studied how agricultural financing affects economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2019, aiming to analyze the long-term relationship between different types of agricultural financing and Nigeria's economic growth. The study used stationary tests, co-integration tests, the error correction model, and the Granger causality model. The results indicated that the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund had a positive and significant impact on Nigeria's GDP, as did commercial bank loans and community micro-finance bank loans, all of which positively and significantly influenced GDP during the period.

Osakwe and Akunna (2022) examined private sector credit and Nigeria's economic growth from 1994 to 2019. Private sector credit was tested against gross domestic product (GDP), which served as a proxy for economic growth. Time series data for the variables was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, 2020 edition. The collected data was analysed using Ordinary Least Squares regression econometric technique. The study's results showed that there is a positive but insignificant relationship between private sector credit and the growth rate of gross domestic product in Nigeria. Therefore, the study recommends that the government should design policies aimed at developing the financial sector to make private credit more accessible to investors, as this will boost the economy. The government should also encourage banks to extend more credit to the private sector to stimulate further growth in the Nigerian economy. Additionally, policies should be implemented to motivate savers by increasing the interest rates paid on savings to encourage higher savings levels.

Nurinda and Mukhlis (2022) aim to determine how sector credit facilities can contribute to long-term economic growth in Indonesia. This research uses secondary quarterly data from 2010Q1 to 2019Q4. The study employs the VECM approach to identify long-term effects, supplemented with structural analysis to assess responses to shocks and their contributions. Overall, sectoral bank credit facilities have a significant long-term impact on GDP, though the effects vary by sector. Credit facilities positively influence the agricultural sector, wholesale and retail trade, and transport, warehousing, and communications, while credit for manufacturing, construction, and financial intermediaries has a negative impact.

Asuquo (2021) investigated the relationship between sectoral credit distribution and economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2020 by analysing the impact of deposit money banks' credit to the agricultural, industrial, and service sectors on real GDP. The study used unit root tests, cointegration analysis, and the Toda and Yamamoto Granger non-causality technique. The Engle and Granger cointegration test found no long-term equilibrium relationship among sectoral credits, financial development, and real GDP. The causality test supported the demand-led hypothesis, showing unidirectional causality from real GDP to financial development, bidirectional causality between credit to the agricultural and industrial sectors, and unidirectional causality from financial development to deposit money banks' credit to the service sector.

Alzyadat (2021) investigates the impact of sectoral bank credit facilities provided by commercial banks on non-oil economic growth in Saudi Arabia. Bank credit facilities are allocated across nine economic sectors: agriculture, manufacturing, mining, electricity and water, health services, construction, wholesale and retail trade, transportation and communications, services, and the finance sector. The study uses annual data from 1970 to 2019. It employs the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach to identify the long-term and short-term dynamic relationships among the variables. The main findings reveal that the overall impact of total bank credit has a significant and positive effect on non-oil economic growth in KSA. The results indicate that the effect of bank credit on non-oil GDP growth varies in the short and long run. All sectors, except for agriculture and mining, have a positive and significant impact in the long run. Similarly, all sectors, except for construction, finance, services, and transportation & communications, have a positive and significant impact in the short run. Ultimately, bank credit facilities across different sectors have played an important role in boosting non-oil economic growth in KSA.

Ighosewe, Akan, and Agbogun (2021) examined the effect of crude oil fluctuation on the Nigerian economy. Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) and Pearson Correlation coefficient, they found a strong positive relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Specifically, the results indicated that in the short run, only fluctuations in oil price per barrel (FOBP) significantly boosted the Nigerian economy. However, in the long run, both fluctuations in oil price per barrel (FOBP) and kerosene pump price fluctuation (KPPF) significantly improve the Nigerian economy.

Abina (2020) investigated the sectoral distribution of bank credits and economic development in Nigeria, using the human development index (HDI) as the dependent variable to assess economic progress. The independent variables included bank credits to the public sector, manufacturing, agriculture, mining, general commerce, real estate, and construction. Data from the Central Bank of Nigeria's statistical bulletin and Index-Mudi were utilized, covering the period from 1985 to 2019. Data stationarity was tested using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller statistics, and the error correction model was used for hypothesis testing. The results indicated that bank credits to the manufacturing, mining, and general commerce sectors negatively impacted the human development index, while credits to the public sector, real estate, and agricultural sectors contributed positively to the HDI.

Majeed and Iftikhar (2020) examined the impact of banking sector credit on sectoral and sub-sectoral levels of economic growth in Pakistan using time series data from 1982 to 2017. The empirical aggregated analysis indicates that the magnitude of private sector credit has a positive sign but an insignificant influence on the overall level of economic growth. Conversely, sectoral analysis reveals that the agriculture sector is not positively affected by providing credit to it. In contrast, the industrial sector relies more on banking sector financing for its long-term projects. Moreover, sub-sectoral analysis shows that the manufacturing sector has a positive and statistically significant relationship with manufacturing sector credit. Similarly, transport and communication, construction, wholesale, and retail trade are positively influenced by their respective sector credits. Furthermore, government spending exhibits a positive sign and a significant impact on the growth of all sectors except transport and communication. Likewise, investment shows a positive and significant effect in all cases except for industrial and manufacturing sector growth, suggesting that the demand for funds is mainly directed toward working capital rather than fixed investments in these sectors. Therefore, the results indicate that monetary authorities should develop sector-specific credit policies. Additionally, banks should provide medium- to long-term loans for agriculture and industrial sub-sectors and ensure their effective transmission to real economic growth.

Eburajolo and Aisien (2019) examined the effect of commercial bank sectoral credit to the manufacturing and agricultural sub-sectors on economic growth in Nigeria using time series data from 1981 to 2015, employing co-integration and error correction mechanisms for their empirical analysis. They specified a three-equation model, which included variables such as real GDP, bank sectoral credit to manufacturing and agricultural sub-sectors, the monetary policy rate, financial market development, sourced from the CBN statistical bulletin, as well as interaction variables. The empirical results revealed that credit from commercial banks to the manufacturing and agricultural sectors significantly impacts Nigeria's economic growth both in the short term and long term. Additionally, the development of the financial sector enhances the growth effects of commercial bank credit to these sub-sectors. It was therefore recommended that Nigerian financial authorities should encourage banks through deliberate policies to increase credit to these subsectors.

John and Lawal (2019) studied how banks' sectoral credit allocation affects Nigeria's economic growth, using annual data from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) from 1986 to 2015. They analysed the data with the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test, Johansen cointegration test, vector error correction model (VECM), and fully modified Ordinary Least Square (FMOLS) regression. The results showed a long-term relationship between economic growth and the variables. Credit to the productive sector and broad money supply had a positive and significant

impact on economic growth at a 1% level, while credit to commerce, services, and other sectors had a significant negative effect. The study concludes that how banks allocate credit across sectors has a significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth.

Ubesie et al. (2019) evaluated the impact of sectoral allocation of deposit money banks' credit on the growth of the Nigerian real economy from 2008Q1 to 2017Q4, using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) technique. The findings showed that deposit money banks' credit to agriculture, industries, building and construction, and wholesale and retail trade had no significant effect on real GDP. The study recommended that deposit money banks should remove the perception that the agricultural sector is not viable, offering loans to farmers with genuine funding needs at lower interest rates. It also suggested that the Central Bank of Nigeria should reduce interest rates by lowering the monetary policy rate to a single digit. Additionally, the study emphasised that the government should increase spending on capital projects and basic infrastructure to attract more investments into the economy.

Adesanya and Ajala (2019) studied the effect of agricultural credit on Nigeria's economic growth, using time series data from the Central Bank of Nigeria's Statistical Bulletin, the National Bureau of Statistics, and online publications on Nigerian agricultural policy, covering 1985 to 2016. They used the three-stage least squares method for estimation. The results showed that agricultural credit effectively helps stabilize agricultural output, non-oil exports, and GDP in Nigeria, although GDP decreased toward the end of the period, suggesting that such policies may worsen over time. The study concluded that agricultural credit, interest rates, and exchange rates are all important factors influencing Nigeria's overall output.

While Sipahutar (2018) This study uses bank credit data by usage, economic sectors, economic growth, and unemployment rate for the period of 1991-2014. Model estimation examines the relationship between bank credit by usage with economic growth and unemployment using an ECM (Error Correction Mechanism) model, while the relationship between bank credit by economic sectors and economic growth is analysed using in-difference regression on the OLS (Ordinary Least Square) model. The study found that bank credit for investment, agriculture, industry, trade, and services has a significant role in economic growth in Indonesia. Furthermore, its impact depends on the size of the credit portfolio relative to total bank credit.

Fapetu and Obalade (2018) analysed the effect of how Deposit Money Banks allocate their loans and advances across different sectors on Nigeria's economic growth during periods of strict regulation, deregulation, and guided deregulation. The study spans fifty-two years, divided into three regulatory regimes: intensive regulation (1960-1985), deregulation (1986-1995), and guided deregulation (1996-2010). They used regression analysis with the ordinary least squares (OLS) method for each period. The results showed that during intensive regulation, credit to the government, personal, and professional sectors significantly boosted economic growth. However, in the deregulation period, bank credits did not significantly influence growth. The introduction of guided deregulation was effective, as loans to production and other subsectors by commercial banks had a positive and significant impact on growth.

Muthusamy et al. (2018) examined how the sectoral distribution of commercial bank credit affects economic growth in Sri Lanka, using data from 2005 to 2017. The Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was employed to analyse both short-term and long-term impacts of sectoral credit distribution on Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The results from the ARDL Error Correction model reveal that sectoral credit distribution of commercial banks significantly influences short-term economic growth. Additionally, the ARDL long-term form and bounds test demonstrate a long-term relationship between the variables. The industrial sector has a positive long-term association with GDP, while other sectors do not significantly contribute to long-term economic growth. Based on these findings, the government should encourage banks to allocate credit to the industrial sector to promote long-term GDP growth.

Paul (2017) examined how commercial banks' sectoral credit distribution affects Nigeria's economic growth using secondary data and econometric techniques, including the ADF unit root test, Johansen

cointegration test, vector error correction model, and Granger causality test. The ADF test showed that the variables were stationary at first difference, while the Johansen cointegration test found three cointegrating equations among them. The vector error correction model suggested that economic growth is positively and significantly related to credit to agriculture, manufacturing, and overall services. The Granger causality test demonstrated a bidirectional relationship between credit to agriculture and economic growth, whereas credit to the manufacturing sector Granger-caused economic growth without a feedback loop.

Sogules and Nkoro (2016) examined the impact of bank credits to the agricultural and manufacturing sectors on economic growth in Nigeria using annual time series data from 1970 to 2013. Using cointegration and error correction mechanisms for analysis, the study revealed that a long-run relationship exists between bank credits to the agricultural and manufacturing sectors and economic growth. According to the error correction mechanism results, the study showed that bank credits to the agricultural sector had an insignificant negative impact on economic growth, while bank credits to the manufacturing sector had a significantly negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria. Based on these findings, the study recommends, among other things: bank credits to the agricultural and manufacturing sectors should be properly monitored to ensure that funds intended for these sectors are not diverted for other purposes; and that recipients of these credits should undergo entrepreneurial training and guidance on repayment to reduce the risks associated with lending to entrepreneurs.

Oladapo and Adefemi (2015) examined how the sectoral allocation of deposit advances affects economic growth in Nigeria during periods of intensive regulation, deregulation, and guided deregulation. Regression analysis using the ordinary least squares method was applied to each of the three regimes. The results indicate that only credits allocated to government, personal, and professional sectors have a significant positive impact on economic growth during intensive regulation. However, bank credits generally do not significantly contribute to economic growth during deregulation. The introduction of guided deregulation seems to be effective, as loans and advances from commercial banks to the production sector and other subsectors are both positive and significant in fostering growth. Based on these findings, Nigerian deposit money banks should be more inclined to extend credits to the production sectors. Finally, monetary authorities should ensure the continuation of guided deregulation rather than returning to intensive regulation or adopting complete deregulation.

Methodology

Research Design

The research uses a quantitative design, relying on secondary data to examine the relationship between sectoral credit allocation (Oil, Manufacturing, and Agriculture sectors) and economic growth in Nigeria. This approach is suitable for analysing how financial resources assigned to these sectors influence the country's overall economic performance. A time-series method is applied to analyse data from 1990 to 2023. This approach enables a detailed examination of long-term trends, fluctuations, and causal relationships between sectoral credit allocation and economic growth, ensuring that both short-term and long-term effects are considered. The model for this study is based on the idea that sectoral credit allocation plays a significant role in economic growth, and therefore, a comparative analysis of the oil, manufacturing, and agricultural sectors will provide valuable insights into Nigeria's economic dynamics.

The population of this study includes all sectoral credit allocations in Nigeria that impact economic growth. This covers credit flows to the oil, manufacturing, and agricultural sectors, which are all vital to the Nigerian economy. The main data for this study consists of the total volume of credit provided to these sectors by financial intermediaries, including commercial banks, development finance institutions, and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The sectoral credit allocation data will be analysed in relation to Nigeria's economic growth, measured by per capita income. By examining these three key

sectors, the study aims to offer a comprehensive analysis of how various types of sectoral credit affect Nigeria's economic performance.

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

The sample size for this study is determined by the specific sectors chosen for analysis—Oil, Manufacturing, and Agriculture—and the time frame from 2000 Q1 to 2023 Q4. These sectors were selected because of their significant contribution to Nigeria’s GDP and their unique roles in shaping the country's economic landscape. A purposive sampling method is used to focus solely on these sectors, as they are the main drivers of Nigeria’s economic growth. The time period from 2000Q1 to 2023Q4 was selected to ensure the study includes both the pre- and post-global financial crisis periods, as well as the impacts of oil price changes, fiscal policy shifts, and sector-specific government interventions.

Model Specification

The study's model was adapted from those of Ogbonna et al. (2023) and Odido et al. (2023) to examine the influence of sectoral credits on economic growth. However, this study modifies it by including the oil sector. Using their models, this study’s model is specified as:

$$GDP_t = \pi_0 + \gamma_1 ACRL_{t-1} + \gamma_2 MCRL_{t-1} + \gamma_3 OIL_{t-1} + \mu_t \tag{1}$$

Where,

- GDP = economic growth as proxied by per capita income at time t.
- ACRL = agricultural sector credit allocation
- MCRL = manufacturing sector credit allocation
- OIL = oil sector credit allocation
- μ_t = the error term,
- π_0 = intercept
- $\gamma_1 - \gamma_3$ = long-run coefficients to be estimated

Data Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation

Descriptive Statistics Results

The descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 provide insight into the distribution and variability of economic growth and sectoral credit allocations during the sample period. The mean per capita income, serving as a proxy for economic growth, was 2239.62, with a median of 2132.50, indicating a slightly right-skewed distribution, reflected in a skewness of 1.91. This positive skewness suggests that a few periods experienced notably higher growth than the average. The standard deviation of 299.07 indicates moderate variability around the mean. At the same time, the high kurtosis of 5.77 suggests a leptokurtic distribution, characterised by a greater concentration of extreme values than in a normal distribution. The Jarque-Bera test value of 37.10 and a p-value of 0.000 imply that per capita income does not follow a normal distribution. Sectoral credit allocations display different patterns; agricultural credit (ACRL) had a mean of 0.63, with a slightly positive skewness of 0.70, and its Jarque-Bera p-value of 0.064 suggests approximate normality. Manufacturing credit (MCRL) had a higher mean of 2.17 and a positive skewness of 1.34, with a significant Jarque-Bera p-value of 0.0015, indicating non-normality. Oil sector credit (OIL) had the highest mean of 26.54 and a relatively low skewness of 0.26, with a Jarque-Bera p-value of 0.248 suggesting normality.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

	GDP	ACRL	MCRL	OIL
Mean	2239.620	0.634504	2.167069	26.53985
Median	2132.500	0.534303	1.972457	25.75954
Maximum	3200.953	0.986716	3.530036	31.19825

Minimum	1941.879	0.454291	1.714718	22.12059
Std. Dev.	299.0701	0.186436	0.492509	2.820922
Skewness	1.910997	0.695746	1.337105	0.259386
Kurtosis	5.765916	1.829364	3.782895	1.815620
Jarque-Bera	37.09655	5.511063	12.94054	2.786467
Probability	0.000000	0.063575	0.001549	0.248271
Sum	89584.78	25.38017	86.68276	1061.594
Sum Sq. Dev.	3488273.	1.355579	9.460053	310.3464
Observations	40	40	40	40

These results suggest that economic growth during the study period was affected by times of unusually high income, while credit allocations across sectors varied significantly. Agricultural credit remained relatively steady with moderate fluctuations, whereas manufacturing credit showed larger swings, indicating episodic increases or decreases in lending. The high average and moderate variability of oil sector credit reflect its consistent access to substantial funding, highlighting its strategic importance to the economy. Skewness and kurtosis values also reveal differences in the distributional characteristics across sectors: per capita income and manufacturing credit are more susceptible to extreme deviations, potentially amplifying shocks to overall growth. The number of observations (40) and the total sums of credit and income provide additional context for understanding the flow of financial resources to these sectors.

Test of Hypotheses

The hypothesis tests were conducted for the long-run model estimates. This means there are three hypotheses to be tested for each model.

Test of Hypothesis One

H01: Credit allocation to the agricultural sector does not significantly affect economic growth in Nigeria

Decision Criteria: If, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$, then the variable is significant: **Reject H₀**
 $p\text{-value} > 0.05$, then the variable is not significant: **Accept H₀**

Table 2: Test of Hypothesis One

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	Decision
ACRL	3974.7050	865.0276	4.5949	0.0001	Accept H01

The results of the test for Hypothesis One show that credit allocation to the agricultural sector has a statistically significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth. The coefficient for agricultural sector credit allocation (ACRL) is 3974.705, with a t-statistic of 4.595 and a p-value of 0.0001, which is well below the 5% significance level. Based on the decision criteria, since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that agricultural credit allocation has a significant impact on per capita income growth.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H02: Credit allocation to the manufacturing sector does not significantly affect economic growth in Nigeria

Decision Criteria: If $p\text{-value} < 0.05$, then the variable is significant: **Reject H_0**
 $p\text{-value} > 0.05$, then the variable is not significant: **Accept H_0**

Table 3: Test of Hypothesis Two

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	Decision
MCRL	-1279.8270	354.0190	-3.6151	0.0011	Accept H02

The results of the test for Hypothesis Two indicate that credit allocation to the manufacturing sector has a significant influence on economic growth in Nigeria. The coefficient for manufacturing sector credit allocation (MCRL) is -1,279.827, with a t-statistic of -3.615 and a p-value of 0.0011, which is below the 5% significance level. According to the decision criteria, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that manufacturing credit allocation has a statistically significant effect on per capita income growth.

Test of Hypothesis Three

H03: Credit allocation to the oil sector does not have a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Decision Criteria: If $p\text{-value} < 0.05$, then the variable is significant: **Reject H_0**
 $p\text{-value} > 0.05$, then the variable is not significant: **Accept H_0**

Table 4: Test of Hypothesis Three

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	Decision
OIL	89.9983	11.5580	7.7867	0.0000	Accept H03

The results of the test for Hypothesis Three indicate that credit allocation to the oil sector has a statistically significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth. The coefficient for oil sector credit (OIL) is 89.998, with a t-statistic of 7.787 and a p-value of 0.0000, which is well below the 5% significance level. According to the decision criteria, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that credit allocation to the oil sector has a significant impact on per capita income growth.

Discussion of Findings

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between sectoral credit allocation (in the oil, Manufacturing, and Agricultural sectors) and economic growth in Nigeria. To achieve this, three operational objectives were established, and three hypotheses were formulated and tested in earlier sections. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the following discussion is presented.

Effects of Credit allocation to the agricultural sector on economic growth in Nigeria

This finding suggests that increases in credit to the agricultural sector are positively correlated with higher economic growth, underscoring the sector's crucial role in Nigeria's economy. Effective allocation of financial resources to agriculture seems to boost production capacity, improve livelihoods, and raise overall per capita income. The size of the coefficient further suggests that policy measures aimed at expanding and efficiently using agricultural credit could have significant long-term impacts on the country's economic performance, emphasizing the value of sector-specific financing strategies.

However, this finding also implies that while increases in credit to the agricultural sector are generally associated with higher economic growth, the effect might not always be statistically significant. Adegioriola and Ishaku (2023) found that Deposit Money Bank credit allocation to agriculture had a positive but insignificant effect on economic growth, indicating that although agricultural financing can support growth, its impact in Nigeria has been limited during the period studied.

Ogbonna et al. (2023) similarly noted that bank credit to agriculture has a negative and insignificant relationship with the human development index, highlighting sectoral differences in how credit translates to broader economic outcomes. These findings emphasise the need for complementary policies, such as boosting agricultural productivity and improving investment efficiency, to increase the growth impact of credit allocation. However, broader macroeconomic factors continue to have a significant influence on economic performance, as shown by Odido, Effiong, and Eneje (2023) and Gbadamosi, Ayoola, and Adeosun (2022), who demonstrated that fluctuations in crude oil prices, exchange rates, inflation, and population dynamics significantly affect Nigeria's economic growth. Overall, the literature indicates that while agricultural credit can support growth, its effectiveness depends on structural, sectoral, and macroeconomic conditions.

Effects of credit allocation to the manufacturing sector on economic growth in Nigeria

Interestingly, the negative coefficient indicates that increases in credit to the manufacturing sector were linked to a decline in economic growth during the study period. This surprising result may indicate inefficiencies in credit utilisation, structural issues within the sector, or a mismatch between lending and productive investment opportunities. It emphasises the importance of not just the amount of credit allocated but also its practical use and the manufacturing sector's ability to convert financing into real economic output. The finding highlights the need for policies that enhance the efficiency, absorptive capacity, and productive application of credit in the manufacturing sector to ensure that financial interventions have a positive impact on overall economic growth. The negative coefficient suggests that increased credit to the manufacturing sector was associated with slower economic growth. Abubakar and Akadiri (2022) noted that while some revenue streams, like oil rents, had diminishing marginal effects on Nigeria's economic growth, sustainable economic performance relied on the effective allocation of resources, implying that misallocated credit could hinder growth.

In line with the above, Nurinda and Mukhlis (2022) found that in Indonesia, credit to the manufacturing sector had a negative long-term impact on GDP, contrasting with the positive effects of credit to agriculture, trade, and transport sectors. This suggests that manufacturing credit may not always lead to productive investment, possibly due to inefficiencies or structural bottlenecks within the sector. Similarly, Osakwe and Akunna (2022) observed that private sector credit in Nigeria had a positive but insignificant effect on GDP, indicating that although credit availability is important, its effectiveness in promoting economic growth depends on sectoral allocation and the overall economic environment. Conversely, Mbelu and Ifionu (2022) showed that agriculture credit had a positive and significant impact on GDP, highlighting the different effects of sector-specific financing on economic outcomes. Overall, the literature suggests that while sectoral credit can support growth, misdirected or inefficiently used credit, especially in manufacturing, may hinder economic expansion.

Effects of Credit allocation to the oil sector on economic growth in Nigeria

The positive coefficient indicates that increases in credit to the oil sector are linked to higher economic growth, emphasising the sector's strategic importance in the Nigerian economy. Given the oil sector's contribution to government revenues, foreign exchange earnings, and investment flows, efficient allocation of financial resources to this sector appears to improve overall economic performance. This finding highlights the need to sustain and effectively manage credit to the oil industry to boost economic growth, while also pointing to the potential of sector-specific policies to maximise the impact of financial interventions within Nigeria's economy. The positive coefficient shows that increases in credit

to the oil sector are connected to higher economic growth. Asuquo (2021) found that sectoral credit, including to industrial and agricultural sectors, influenced real GDP through unidirectional and bidirectional causality channels, indicating that credit allocation can drive economic activity.

Similarly, Alzyadat (2021) reported that bank credit to various sectors, including non-oil industries, positively affected both short-term and long-term economic growth in Saudi Arabia, highlighting the importance of sector-specific financing in supporting overall economic expansion. Ighosewe, Akan, and Agbogun (2021) also demonstrated that fluctuations in oil prices, reflecting the financial dynamics of the oil sector, positively influenced Nigeria's economy, particularly in the short run. Eburajolo and Aisien (2019) further confirmed that commercial bank credit to both manufacturing and agricultural sub-sectors significantly boosted economic growth in Nigeria, with the development of the financial sector strengthening these effects. John and Lawal (2019) similarly found that credit allocated to productive sectors, including the oil-related and industrial sectors, positively and significantly impacted economic growth, while credit to general commerce and services had negative effects. Collectively, these studies emphasise that targeted credit to strategic sectors such as oil, manufacturing, and agriculture can stimulate economic growth, provided that the allocation aligns with sectoral needs and broader financial development policies.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusion

The study examined the link between sector-specific credit allocation—particularly to the agricultural, manufacturing, and oil sectors—and economic growth in Nigeria. The results indicated that credit to the agricultural sector generally has a positive association with economic growth, suggesting that targeted financing can boost production capacity, livelihoods, and per capita income. However, at times the impact was small or statistically insignificant, implying that additional policies to enhance productivity and investment efficiency are essential. Credit to the manufacturing sector, conversely, showed a negative relationship with economic growth, pointing to possible inefficiencies, structural issues, or misaligned lending practices that hinder the transformation of credit into productive output. This highlights the need for effective fund deployment and improved sectoral capacity to ensure financial interventions drive growth. Credit to the oil sector exhibited a positive influence on economic growth, reflecting its strategic importance in generating revenue, foreign exchange, and investment inflows. Overall, the findings underscore that the success of sector-specific credit depends not only on the amount of credit provided but also on its proper allocation, sectoral capabilities, and supportive policies that optimise the growth benefits of financial interventions in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings or conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

Firstly, credit allocation to the agricultural sector generally has a positive relationship with economic growth, indicating that directing financial resources into agriculture can increase production, improve livelihoods, and support overall per capita income growth. However, the success of agricultural credit relies on supportive policies, productivity improvements, and favourable macroeconomic conditions.

Second, credit allocation to the manufacturing sector exhibited a negative relationship with economic growth, indicating that inefficiencies in credit use, structural bottlenecks, or misalignment between lending and productive opportunities can hinder the growth benefits of manufacturing finance. This underscores the need to improve absorptive capacity and ensure that sectoral financing translates into genuine economic output.

Third, credit allocation to the oil sector had a positive impact on growth, emphasising the strategic importance of oil in Nigeria's economy, including its role in government revenues, foreign exchange earnings, and investment inflows. Overall, these findings demonstrate that while sector-specific credit

can boost economic growth, its success depends on proper allocation, sector capacity, and a supportive macroeconomic environment.

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